

iJER Research

International Journal of Education and Research
Vol-1, Number 3, December- 2024 | Peer-Reviewed
Journal ISSN 2764-9733 | ijerresearch.org
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14359825

6TH INTERNATIONAL EDUCATION AND RESEARCH SEMINAR - “AUTONOMOUS LEARNING IN EDUCATION”

Listener: Eliane Alves de Souza

1st Lecture: “Analysis and Discussion of Results: how to prepare”

Speaker: Dra. Augustina Subeldia

REVIEW:

First, let's understand the which means “Results “Scientific Research””: These are the raw data obtained during the research, demonstrated through tables, graphs, figures or other resources. The results reveal what was found in the research and indicate whether the research is relevant or not. It is a more objective and descriptive section of the academic work, focusing on the presentation of the data collected.

The “Analysis and Discussion of Results” section presents, comments on and interprets the data collected during the research. And what is the difference between the “Analysis” and the “Discussion” of the results? The Analysis aims to organize and summarize the data obtained in a way that provides answers to the problem proposed for the investigation. Discussion of Results he has one character interpretative and analytical, looking for explain, contextualize and analyze the meaning of the Results.

The study investigative this grounded in the search characterized and classified according to some criteria:

STRATEGY INVESTIGATIVE: Survey – Intervention

METHODS: Statisticians – Deductive – Analytical – Hypothetical – Inductive – Synthetic

APPROACH: Quantitative – Qualitative – Mixed

SOURCE OF INFORMATION: Laboratory – Library – Field – Data Audiences

DATA ORIGINALITY: Primary – Secondary – Tertiary

OBJECTIVES: Exploratory - Correlational – Descriptive – Explanatory

NATURE: Basic – Applied

PROCEDURES TECHNICIANS: Bibliographical – Experimental – Almost Experimental – Ethnographic – Participant – Documentary

TEMPORALITY: Longitudinal – Transversal